

Gas exchange and water use efficiency acclimation of In Vitro clones of *Gmelina arborea* seedlings

Intercambio gaseoso y uso eficiente del agua en la aclimatación de plántulas producidas *in vitro* de clones de *Gmelina arborea*

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Abstract.

Introduction: Forest trees and timber production require superior plant material that can adapt to changing atmospheric conditions, such as drought and increased vapor pressure deficit (VPD), conditions that always emerge with the transfer of *in vitro* plants to nursery conditions. **Objective:** To investigate how air vapor pressure deficit affects leaf gas exchange and water use efficiency of *in vitro* clones of *Gmelina arborea* during their adjustment to a nursery environment. **Methods:** Twelve clones of *G. arborea* produced *in vitro* were transplanted into Jiffy pellets and transferred to top-bench plastic tunnels. Gas exchange variables were measured on leaf seedlings during three periods after transfer. Variables were recorded at photosynthetic capacity adjusting the leaves at two levels of vapor pressure deficit (1.5 and 3.0 kPa) within the leaf chamber. **Results:** *in vitro* seedlings showed a wide variation in instantaneous gas exchange responses across the twelve clones, just after transfer to greenhouse tunnels, and later during nursery acclimation. During the application of instantaneous high VPD treatment, there was a strong reduction in A_{\max} with a corresponding decrease in stomatal conductance, strong increases in transpiration, and reduced

water use efficiencies across clones. At weeks 4-5, responses were similar, but most variables showed the absence of interaction effects between clones and VPD treatment. After a month, seedlings recover gas exchange values to previous tunnel conditions. **Conclusions:** a combination of gas exchange responses to short-term changes to higher VPD results in different performances among the tested *G. arborea* clones, and some of them showed a great capacity to adjust to high VPD. It is essential to perform stress experiments to identify superior clone material because the ranking of clones did change after the VPD treatments were applied.

Keywords: nursery acclimation, photosynthetic assimilation, stomatal conductance, tropical timbers, water use efficiency.

Resumen.

Introducción: Los árboles forestales y la producción de madera requieren material vegetal superior que pueda adaptarse a las cambiantes condiciones atmosféricas, como la sequía y el aumento del déficit de presión de vapor (DPV), condiciones que siempre surgen durante la transferencia de plantas producidas *in vitro* a las condiciones de vivero. Objetivo: Investigar cómo el déficit de presión de vapor del aire afecta el intercambio gaseoso foliar y la eficiencia en el uso del agua de clones de *Gmelina arborea* producidos *in vitro* durante su ajuste a un ambiente de vivero. Métodos: Doce clones de *G. arborea* producidos *in vitro* fueron trasplantados a pellets Jiffy y transferidos a túneles de enraizamiento. Las variables de intercambio gaseoso se midieron en las hojas de las plántulas durante tres períodos posteriores a la transferencia. Las variables se registraron a capacidad fotosintética, ajustando las hojas a dos niveles de déficit de presión de vapor (1,5 y 3,0 kPa) dentro de la cámara foliar. **Resultados:** Las plántulas producidas *in vitro* mostraron una amplia variación en las respuestas instantáneas de intercambio gaseoso entre los doce clones, tanto inmediatamente después de su transferencia a los túneles de enraizamiento como posteriormente durante la aclimatación en vivero. Durante la aplicación del tratamiento instantáneo de DPV elevado, se observó una fuerte reducción de la tasa máxima de fotosíntesis (A_{max}), acompañada de una disminución en la conductancia estomática, un marcado incremento en la transpiración y una reducción de la eficiencia en el uso del agua en todos los clones. Entre las semanas 4 y 5, las respuestas fueron similares, pero la mayoría de las variables mostraron ausencia de efectos de interacción entre los clones y el tratamiento de DPV. Después de un mes, las plántulas recuperaron los valores de intercambio gaseoso observados previamente en las condiciones de túnel. **Conclusiones:** La combinación de respuestas de intercambio gaseoso frente a cambios de corto plazo hacia un mayor déficit de presión de vapor produjo diferentes desempeños entre los clones evaluados de *G. arborea*, y algunos de ellos mostraron una gran capacidad de ajuste a condiciones de DPV elevado. Es fundamental realizar experimentos de estrés para identificar material clonal superior, ya que la clasificación o jerarquización de los clones cambió después de la aplicación de los tratamientos de DPV.

Palabras clave: Aclimatación en vivero, asimilación fotosintética, conductancia estomática, maderas tropicales, eficiencia en el uso del agua.

1. Introduction

Forest ecosystems and timber production have been greatly impacted by rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and more frequent extreme weather events (Kirilenko & Sedjo, 2007). These climatic variations, plus increasing atmospheric carbon concentration, require the study and selection of possible sources of better plant materials to face the adverse conditions (Chapman *et al.*, 2012, Austin, *et al.* 2020). Tropical trees are not the exception (Keenan, 2015), and detailed studies have strongly focused on strategies to attenuate climate variability in agronomic plant species (Sekhar *et al.*, 2021), as in tropical forests and tree plantations (Guariguata *et al.*, 2008). As a large economic sector worldwide, tropical forestry depends on better growth and resistance of tree species to physical factors during plant reproduction and propagation, seedling and sapling acclimation, and final field growth.

There is a need to look for promising forestry material that focuses on the responses of seedlings and saplings of tropical woods to the initial growth conditions inside and outside the nursery. This step is especially important in clonally produced plants in the laboratory since they are plants that for the first time face the harsh natural environmental conditions of temperature, environmental humidity, and others such as nutrients and wind. The use of clones instead of seeds ensures the transfer of the total genetic variance, which results in a general improvement of productivity, quality, and strength of the wood (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2013); but there is a cost of the risk of plantation failure, diversity loss and risk associated to vegetative propagation (Wu, 2019). For example, *Eucalyptus* plantations in Brazil have been transformed substantially after the research with clonal plantations with interspecific hybrids in regions under water and nutritional stresses (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2013).

From a mechanistic point of view, research on seedlings and saplings to be used in reforestation and restoration projects has focused on the factors that determine their growth and productivity. One of the critical mechanisms that determine plant growth and productivity is photosynthesis, which is highly sensitive to environmental factors, including light, temperature, humidity, and vapor pressure deficit (VPD). VPD is the difference between the saturated vapor pressure and the actual vapor pressure in the air, and it has been shown to influence leaf photosynthetic sensitivity and water use efficiency (Grossiord *et al.*, 2020), because under conditions of high VPD, conductance decreases, transpiration increases up to a certain threshold specific to the species, which in turn reduces the plant's ability to photosynthesize and can ultimately result in decreased plant growth and yield (Grossiord *et al.*, 2020), however, variable between species (Franks & Farquhar, 1999).

Similarly, stomatal conductance (g) is a key physiological process that regulates the exchange of water vapor and carbon dioxide between plants and the atmosphere and represents the most important factor that determines the greatest first control point to deal with a water deficit in the soil-plant-atmosphere continuum (Urban *et al.*, 2017). Studies on global warming and the increase in atmospheric CO₂ suggest that stomatal conductance results in an increase in the efficiency of photosynthetic water use (Flexas *et al.*, 2015). At the global scale, terrestrial gross primary production has been reduced widely due to higher VPD, which may nullify the positive CO₂ fertilization effect (Yuan *et al.*, 2020). In this context, studying the response of plant species to changes in VPD is complex and critical to developing strategies to maintain plant productivity in a changing climate.

Among the most studied tropical timber species, early work on gas exchange responses of seedlings of *G. arborea* had shown typical response to increases in temperature and irradiance (Osonubi & Davies, 1980), showing a mild reduction in photosynthesis but a general increase in stomatal

conductance when grown under mild water stress. They also found that the stomata of *Gmelina* were apparently insensitive to variation in VPD, and WUE was comparatively high, even when VPD was high, and the stomata were fully open. Recently, Ávila *et al.* (2016;2017) suggest that water use efficiency (WUE) as the rate of carbon fixed by water transpired was established as an important indicator of plant performance at an early (nursery) stage of plants versus the adult counterparts in the field for *G. arborea* (Ávila *et al.*, 2016;2017) in Costa Rica. However, there are no studies addressing how VPD may influence the gas exchange response of *in vitro* clones after transplantation in nurseries.

The negative effect of VPD on yield and primary productivity is partially mediated by stomatal acclimation (López *et al.*, 2021). In this circumstance, this research we explored the impact of contrasting air VPD on leaf gas exchange parameters at photosynthetic capacity and its corresponding effects on water use efficiency in *Gmelina arborea* clones, a commercially important timber species and discuss the implications of these findings for managing plant growth and productivity under varying environmental conditions and its association in future warming conditions.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Plant material

The company Forestry Service Costa Rica provided 25 mother plants of 18 clones from its breeding program, which were transferred to the Research Nursery of the Instituto de Investigaciones y Servicios Forestales, at Universidad Nacional, Heredia (10.473663398010622, -84.01677019428516). The mother plants were placed under greenhouse conditions with daily manual irrigation, a solution of 2g/l of agrymicin® and 2g/l of benlate® was applied twice a week, in order to maintain the mother plants in the best phytosanitary conditions. In addition, 6-Benzyl amino purine (6-BAP) 50 ppm was applied once a week as a growth regulator to stimulate sprouting.

2.2. *In vitro* establishment.

In the *in vitro* establishment, nodal segments (nodes) and apices of approximately 2.5cm were used as initial explants. The explants were transferred from the greenhouse to the laboratory inside a beaker and the apices were separated from the nodes for the disinfection process. Both types of explants were placed under running water for 30 min. Subsequently, inside the laminar flow chamber, water and antibacterial soap were added and kept in constant agitation for 5 min, the soapy water was discarded.

For the apices, 70% ethanol (EtOH) was added for 1 min, followed by 15 min with sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) at 1% a.i. plus Tween®, finally the NaClO was discarded and three washes with sterile distilled water were performed. For the nodes after washing with soap and water, 15% calcium hypochlorite (Ca(ClO)²) plus Tween® was added for 15 minutes under agitation and three washes with sterile distilled water.

The explants were established in MS basic culture medium (1962) supplemented with 3% sucrose, 1 g/l activated charcoal and 2.88 g/l Phytigel™ at pH 5.7.

2.3. Acclimation experiment in tunnels.

During the micropropagation process, the explants were placed in glass jars covered with thin, transparent plastic with small holes that allow gas exchange with the nutrient medium and the

external medium, where they remained for a period of three weeks for growth and rooting. Subsequently, the *in vitro* plants were transferred to pellets known by their commercial name as Jiffy's and placed in micro tunnels or acclimatization chambers covered with transparent plastic; at this stage, sprinkler irrigation was applied with a regime of three irrigations per day, at 7, 12 and 16 hours, for a period of 3 minutes each. At the end of these two weeks, a general survey of gas exchange measurements at full light was done. Two more sets of gas exchange data were taken at two levels of vapor pressure deficit.

2.4. Leaf gas exchange measurements.

Foliar gas exchange variables were measured *in situ* on mature, healthy, well-expanded, and light-exposed leaves chosen from the upper two nodes from every seedling from each clone, using a portable photosynthesis system (LiCor 6800 XT, LiCor Inc. Nebraska, USA), during morning hours, between 9:00 to 12:30 h. Early in the morning, the ambient vapor pressure deficit (VPDa) was between 0.9 and 1.2 kPa. By midday, VPDa reached values between 2 and 3 kPa. Gas exchange measurements were done by using a constant incident radiation $1000 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ of photosynthetically photon flux density (PPFD) as measured inside the apparatus sensor head. Before all measurements, a couple of light curve responses were done on several clones by varying incident photosynthetic photon flux density automatically from 1500 to 0 $\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. In all cases, maximum assimilation (A_{max}) was always below the chosen light level. The measurements of the clones were randomly chosen every day to mix effects of varying VDPa's among clones and morning hours.

The first set of measurements was done just after two weeks under greenhouse tunnel conditions (period 1) and consisted of measurements of clones without any treatment. After week two, tunnels were eliminated and seedlings remained only with the applied watering regime.

The following two sets of data (periods 2 and 3) were done after week 3 and weeks 4 to 5, in the greenhouse. The experiment consisted of sequential measurements of the leaf gas exchange parameters at two levels of ambient vapor pressure deficit (VPDa) controlled automatically by the photosynthesis system. After initial induction to constant A_{max} , the first measurements were taken after at least 2 (2-5) minutes at approximately 1.5 kPa and a second measurement immediately after 2 (2 to 5) min equilibrium at approximately 3.0 kPa. Each leaf required 5 to 10 minutes to reach a maximum photosynthetic induction, and three sets of data were logged at 15-30 s intervals. In the second period, seedlings were 3 weeks old after transfer and one week exposed to non-tunnel conditions. In the third period, the plants were 4 to 5 weeks old and 2-3 weeks after emerging from the tunnels. The leaf gas exchange parameters of *G. arborea* seedlings were measured at two levels of ambient VPD. The first measurements were taken after at least 2 minutes at approximately 1.5 kPa and a second measurement immediately after 2 min equilibrium at approximately 3.0 kPa. Each leaf required 5 to 10 minutes to reach a maximum photosynthetic induction, and three sets of data were saved at 15 to 30 s intervals. The measured variables were maximum assimilation (A_{max}), stomatal conductance (g), internal CO_2 concentration (C_i), the ratio of C_i to ambient CO_2 concentration, C_a (C_i/C_a), transpiration rate (E), and a calculated variable known as photosynthetic water use efficiency (WUE). All variables and units are reported in Table 1.

2.5. Statistical analysis.

Data from the first period were studied with one-way analyses of variance per variable with clones as the main factor. Subsequently, a general ANCOVA was executed for all variables using g as a covariable and VPD levels as a categorical variable. For the last set of measurements from the

third period, a two-way analysis of variance was performed where the clone and the treatment (VPD of 1.5 and 3.0 kPa) were the main factors.

3. Results

After two weeks of transplanting to JIFFY substrate and growth inside plastic tunnels, seedlings of *G. arborea* as a whole showed differences between clones and a wide variation of A_{max} values, ranking between 11.15 and 15.9 $\mu\text{ mol m}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$ (**Table 1**). Stomatal conductance when way up close to 0.23 $\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$. Clones with higher A_{max} and WUE tend to have higher stomatal conductance (**Figure 1**). Clones 7, 9, and 16 show the greater A_{max} . The depicted relation between E and g showed a straight relationship where clones 9, 10, 11, and 16 were positioned at the top of this relation. This positioning changes with the variable studied. When relating A_{max} , E, and WUE against g (**Figure 1**), a clear pattern emerges, producing a sequential and linear response between g and E (**Figure 1B**). This relation groups the twelve clones into three groups, with clones 9,10,11 and 16 at the top of this relationship, which is also confirmed in the two other relations (**Figure 1A** and **Figure 1C**).

Table 1. Mean (\pm standard error) of four foliar gas exchange variables of *Gmelina arborea* seedlings after two weeks after transplanting to Jiffy media: A_{max} , maximum assimilation of photosynthesis ($\mu\text{ mol CO}_2\text{ m}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$); g, stomatal conductance ($\text{mmol m}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$); transpiration (E, $\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$), and the water use efficiency (A_{max}/E).

Clone number	A_{max}	g	E	WUE
1	11.149 \pm 0.835	0.155 \pm 0.017	3.617 \pm 0.51	2.531 \pm 0.068
3	13.380 \pm 0.950	0.165 \pm 0.012	3.769 \pm 0.17	2.949 \pm 0.058
5	12.492 \pm 0.847	0.164 \pm 0.01	3.844 \pm 0.29	2.935 \pm 0.0310
7	14.820 \pm 0.949	0.192 \pm 0.017	4.564 \pm 0.47	2.287 \pm 0.169
8	13.402 \pm 0.552	0.176 \pm 0.012	4.264 \pm 0.36	3.338 \pm 0.477
9	15.583 \pm 1.051	0.202 \pm 0.017	4.874 \pm 0.55	3.760 \pm 0.234
10	13.084 \pm 0.162	0.208 \pm 0.011	4.998 \pm 0.43	2.972 \pm 0.082
11	11.218 \pm 0.678	0.216 \pm 0.009	5.145 \pm 0.34	3.701 \pm 0.172
13	11.778 \pm 0.758	0.177 \pm 0.009	4.494 \pm 0.15	2.868 \pm 0.133
15	11.479 \pm 0.529	0.176 \pm 0.024	4.400 \pm 0.26	2.944 \pm 0.175
16	14.224 \pm 0.655	0.218 \pm 0.008	5.357 \pm 0.34	2.954 \pm 0.158
17	12.783 \pm 0.458	0.179 \pm 0.02	4.563 \pm 0.32	2.803 \pm 0.068
ANOVA Tests between clones				
F ratio	3.79	2.025	2.201	4.31
P value	0.001	0.047	0.030	0.000
R2	0.470	0.322	0.340	0.502
ANCOVA test				

g	0.000	-	0.000	0.506
Clone	0.000	-	0.870	0.001
RSquare	0.691	-	0.634	0.959

* One-Way ANOVA is presented to compare variation between clones, showing a strong differentiation among clones. The lower part of this table presents an Analysis of Covariance where the main variables were tested against the stomatal conductance as the covariate and the Clon number as the categorical effect.

*Table 1 shows ANCOVA tests for the corresponding relations.

Figure 1. Relationship between stomatal conductance and a) Maximum assimilation rates ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), b) Transpiration rate ($\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), and c) photosynthetic water use efficiency (WUE defined as A_{max}/E).

During period 2, instantaneous leaf gas exchange was sequentially measured at 1.5 and 3.0 kPa of vapor pressure de deficit. The relationship between maximum assimilation and stomatal conductance showed a contrasting behavior, where seedlings from clones at 1.5 kPa responded with a higher slope and less general variation across clones (**Figure 2A**). Across clones and treatments, A_{max} values varied between 2.5 and $9.5 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. It seems that the greater

reduction of this relationship occurred to a strong negative effect of greater VPD in stomatal conductance. In this sense, A_{max} showed a mean general reduction of about 30 % when leaves are exposed to a higher VPD, with clones 6, 9, and 16 reaching the 40/50 % reduction. However, stomatal conductance at high VPD reached a mean value of 100 % reduction, with clones 10 and 16 with extreme changes in this variable (**Figure 2B**).

The relationships between stomatal conductance g versus the other four variables show an overwhelming effect of g across clones. A_{max} and C_i did not show a significant effect of the VPD treatment across clones, but VPD strongly affects the rate of transpiration and water use efficiency (**Table 2**). It is worth noting that the initial photosynthetic response of some clones does not predict a concomitant response when measured under higher VPD. This is the case for clones 9 and 16, both showing high A_{max} values but severely affected by higher VPD conditions reducing drastically A_{max} or g , respectively (**Figure 2B**).

*The ANCOVA test for these relationships is shown in Table 2.B) Percentage change in the mean values of maximum assimilation (A_{max}) and stomatal conductance (g) of leaves of *G. arborea* seedlings after instantaneous measurements at 1.5 (green dots) versus 3.0 kPa (black dots) of VPD on the leaf, during acclimation to shade house conditions outside tunnels for 13 clones of in vitro seedling.

Figure 2. A) Relationship between maximum assimilation (A_{max}) and stomatal conductance (g) for the thirteen clones of *Gmelina arborea* seedlings three weeks after transplantation.

Figure 2.

Table 2. P values effects for the tests of ANCOVA and Determination Coefficient (RSquared) between g versus A_{max} , C_i , E , and WUE after 3 weeks in tunnels for all clones classified by treatment of VPD.

Variable	A max	Ci	E	WUE
P value Stomatal conductance	0.0000	0.000	0.000	0.000
VPD Treatment	0.101	0.269	0.000	0.000
R Square	0.312	0.347	0.853	0.436

During the third period of acclimation, all gas exchange variables show a significant effect of the VPD treatment, with strong reductions in almost all variables when plants are exposed to higher VPD near the leaf (**Table 3**). Additionally, the analysis of this last set of data was adjusted to obtain an interaction term between the clone responses and the treatment effect, to test whether clones change their responses to VPD in different ways. In this sense, clones did differ between VPD treatments in all variables except for the A_{max} . However, all clones adjusted strongly in their response to gas exchange variables except for WUE. E , g , C_i and C_iC_a show strong effects on both factors. WUE was greatly reduced by a higher VPD, but this reduction was similar across clones (**Table 3**). The differences in the response to low and high VPD conditions registered as percent change (**Figure 3**) mostly showed significant reductions (**Table 3**), but transpiration increased, only in clones 7 and 17.

In this third period, the range of values of A_{max} reaches similar values as the ones of the first period. A_{max} values ranged from 10.5 to 15.8 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ across clones, this range was reduced from less than 1 to almost 10 and raised again by the third period ranging from 9.5 to 15.8 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. However, stomatal conductance did not reach values from the first and second periods and transpiration remained high and represented the greatest positive percent change between treatments (**Figure 3**).

To better explain gas exchange responses between clones, stomatal conductance change versus A_{max} , transpiration and WUE (**Figure 3BCD**) evidenced the way this clone response where responding to sudden changes in VPD. In these relationships, clones 7, 11 and 17 were at the far reduced end of A_{max} and g , the linear relation where all clones aligned, and in the smaller reduction change portion of the WUE. Contrarily, clones 1, 3, and 10 did not change A_{max} or stomatal conductance but suffered severe increases in transpiration resulting in important reduction in WUE.

Table 3. Probabilities of a Two Way ANOVA on six leaf gas exchange variables for *Gmelina arborea*. Clone and treatment (TRT, VPD effect) as the main factors, TRTxClone is their interaction. A_{max} , maximum assimilation; g , stomatal conductance; C_i , internal Carbon, C_iC_a , the ratio of C_i to C_a (Ambient Carbon); E , transpiration; WUE , water use efficiency.

Cuadro 3.

Variable	TRT	Clone	TRTxClone	R squared
A_{max}	0.085	0.014	0.986	0.414
g	0.001	0.001	0.821	0.588
C_i	0.001	0.048	0.530	0.581
C_iC_a	0.000	0.027	0.441	0.597
E	0.000	0.004	0.526	0.578
WUE	0.000	0.219	0.664	0.580

*Bold numbers indicate P values lower than 0.05. Coefficient of determination (R squared) is also shown. Unit as in Table 1.

*A) Mean global change of the five gas exchange variables. Relationships between stomatal conductance response changes versus B) maximum assimilation, A_{max} % c) transpiration change (E , %), and D) water use efficiency change (WUE, %).

Figure 3. Response change (RC %) of gas exchange variables of *G. arborea in vitro* seedlings measured at 1.5 Kpa and 3.0 kPa of VPD treatments during the third period at weeks 4-5 after transfer to greenhouse benches without tunnels, showing mean global response by clone number.

4. Discussion

The interaction between environmental factors and genetic traits determines tree productivity, which is crucial in the face of climate change (Alfaro *et al.*, 2014). We found significant variation in gas exchange parameters among the thirteen clones of *G. arborea* produced by cloning. These measurements were taken several weeks after transfer from *in vitro* conditions to greenhouse tunnels and outside. In general, a combination of gas exchange responses to short-term changes in higher vapor pressure deficit resulted in different performances among the tested clones. Similar results on photosynthesis and stomatal conductance have been reported in clones from timber species, such as rubber trees (Kositsup *et al.*, 2010) and teak (Huang *et al.*, 2019). The maximum assimilation rates averaged around $12.9 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ across clones. After a week outside the tunnels, A_{max} ranged from 7 to $4 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ in the 1.5 and 3 kPa VPD treatment, respectively. Surprisingly, it took approximately one to two weeks more to recover to similar initial values. The changes in stomatal conductance followed those of A_{max} . Concomitantly, strong reductions in transpiration and resulting water use efficiency segregated all the clones in a continuous gradient, but the relative positions of the different clones changed between these last two variables. Variables such as internal carbon (C_i) and the ratio between C_i and C_a were almost constant throughout the experimental time until the end when these two parameters showed some response, but the response change was always below 20 %.

Recent data on net assimilation rates measured in nursery conditions (Ávila *et al.*, 2016) coincide with the rates we observed and those reported elsewhere (Rojas *et al.*, 2012). However, plants grown in the field can double the rates observed in the nursery (Ávila *et al.*, 2016), indicating that

nursery plants may perform less well than field-grown plants. This effect was also observed in some Mediterranean seedlings and saplings during experimental drought stress. The relationship between leaf area and pot volume directly influences gas exchange responses (Varone *et al.*, 2012), which becomes critical as plants age.

During the VPD treatments of the last two periods, A_{max} decreased again mostly related to stomatal limitations. The typical asymptotic response between A_{max} and g was found for all clones together, supporting the general trend found across different plant habits and species (Tay *et al.*, 2007; Kositsup *et al.*, 2010). This same behavior was found in clonal hydroponic seedlings of *Eucalyptus camaldulensis* under PEG-induced drought (Utkhao & Yingjajaval, 2015). Other studies confirm the reduction in A_{max} due to stomatal limitations but also show that larger saplings reduced A_{max} due to nonstomatal limitations such as mesophyll conductance and changes in the electron transport rate, during water stress in some Mediterranean tree species (Varone *et al.*, 2012).

On the other hand, it is possible to mention that increasing VPD significantly increased E and this may have caused the reduction in PN . Clonal plants seem to adjust to these changes rapidly as far seedlings remain longer in the nursery environment. By the end of the experiment a month later, practically both effects (clones and VPD treatment) adjusted in such a way that interaction effects were nullified. In general, species may have differences in their acclimation capacities in close dependence on the prevailing climate (Crous, 2019) and how they interact to respond to present growing conditions in trees (Blackman *et al.*, 2017). Phenotypic plasticity and its variation may play an important role in changes in the gas exchange value as demonstrated for light acclimation in tropical tree seedlings (Valladares *et al.*, 2000). In Costa Rican populations of *G. arborea*, anatomical traits of the wood varied significantly among climatic provenances and a clear separation occurred between dry versus wet forest trees (Moya & Fo, 2008), traits highly related to hydraulic performance. There is accumulating evidence that the photosynthesis rate is determined by reductions in stomatal conductance and in the leaf-to-air vapor pressure deficit (Slot & Winter, 2017; Hernández *et al.*, 2020) more than through direct effects of temperature. Strong plasticity responses have been found for species such as *Tabebuia rosea* (Slot *et al.*, 2021), showing a significant source of phenotypic variation between shade and sun-grown leaves.

In addition, we found that ranking species performance by a general survey of A_{max} measurements or constructing light response curves is insufficient to evaluate clone responses to sudden changes in water stress or another abiotic factor due to changes in the response pattern of some clones during simulated stress conditions. Therefore, it is essential to perform more detailed stress experiments to identify superior clone material. Clone ranking changed and revealed that there is an important interaction response only identifiable when gas exchange parameters are measured in the context of any kind of treatment. In this sense, the conservation of plant species using *ex-situ* and *in-situ* strategies has revealed the need to understand how plants are better kept and how they respond to abiotic factor and their consequences for tree species in practical situations such as for greenhouse and nursery propagation and growth. Several new actions have been developed in the field of seed biology (Pritchard *et al.*, 2014), but there is an overwhelming task in the realm of the leaf gas exchange traits. For example, new evidence shows that plant hydraulics influence the water stress responses over a broad range of temporal scales by acclimating canopy conductance to light and VPD as soil humidity changes (Detto & Paccala, 2022). As a consequence, the functional composition of the communities and their assemblage is influenced by atmospheric and soil drought risks (Méndez *et al.*, 2020). For *G. arborea*, finding new clones with the ability to adjust

to changes in atmospheric drought stress emerges as a key factor to study their success at different stages of the production of plant material, e.g., for restoration initiatives.

This study suggests that some practices can be performed in greenhouses and nurseries that may help ameliorate and improve seedlings endurance during the most critical period from seedling to the sapling. For example, manipulation of pot or bag size, optimal watering frequency, and light and wind conditions certainly will affect leaf stomatal conductance and consequently transpiration and photosynthetic water use efficiency. In this case, plastic enclosures seem to reduce the impact of sudden changes from *in vitro* seedlings to greenhouse seedlings planted on bags.

5. Conclusions

In vitro-produced clones of *Gmelina arborea* exhibited substantial variation in their physiological responses to increased vapor pressure deficit (VPD), revealing genetic differences in their acclimation capacity during the transition from *in vitro* culture to nursery conditions. Elevated VPD significantly reduced the maximum photosynthetic rate and stomatal conductance, increased transpiration, and decreased water use efficiency, confirming the high sensitivity of leaf gas exchange to atmospheric water stress.

Although the seedlings gradually recovered their physiological performance during acclimation, the relative ranking of the clones changed under stress conditions, indicating that evaluations conducted only under non-stress conditions may not accurately reflect their adaptive potential. Therefore, incorporating physiological assessments under water or atmospheric stress provides a valuable tool for identifying superior clonal material in forest tree breeding programs. Overall, these findings provide useful physiological criteria for selecting clones with greater resilience to climate change and for optimizing the production of high-quality planting material for commercial plantations and forest restoration programs.

6. Ethics and conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have fully complied with all relevant ethical and legal requirements, both during the study and in the production of the manuscript; that there are no conflicts of interest of any kind; that all funding sources are fully and clearly stated in the acknowledgments section; and that they fully agree with the final edited version of the article.

7. Acknowledgments

We thank the Fondo Especial para la Educación Superior (FEES) for funding the research, and the Photosynthesis system equipment acquisition, and to the Vice-Rector's Office for Research of the National University of Costa Rica, through the "Redes" Project (SIA Code No. 0433-21).

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